

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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"IF I COULD"

I'm trying to hide the real feeling for you
I'm trying to let you see what is untrue of me
It hurts but I could never do anything
Just to let you know that I love you so

If I could only break my heart for you
If I could only show you what is inside
Bu there is no way to unfold my feelings
Only to let it go and let you know nothing

I am in love with you but burdens roll over
No one ever knows who I am and why
This love that consumes me now and before
If I could only be real to express what is true

If I could only have the courage to speak
If I could only have you and listen
If I could only be me and tell you
But then and again, If I just could...

